

Registration form for data protection training

Subject Area:

Institute:

Contact:

Telephone Number:

E-Mail:

Research data Protection

Other training relating tot he topic of Research Data Management and legal aspects (please explain further):

Number of participants:

Date proposed (right appointment , however, only after personal consultation):

Comment:

Place, Date: